

ISic0641

I.Sicily inscription 0641

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

found during construction work at the villa of Prof. Angelo Maiorana,
Ognina, Gatania

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, private villa (Prof. A. Maiorana)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332932

1. Σεπτίκις □ Ὡραίς
2. χρηστὸς καὶ ἄμε-
3. πτος ²⁶ἄμεμπτος²⁶ □ ἔζησεν
4. ἔτη □ νε' #⁵⁶ μῆνες #⁵⁶
5. γ' #⁵⁶ ἡμέρες
6. ε#⁵⁶ λ' #⁵⁶
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644883
PHI 332932

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1994.0764

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 44.0762

Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité.* 106: 79-118. At 85-86 no.4 fig.7

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